

The Adaptability of Public School Teachers amidst the Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the adaptability of public-school teachers from a national high school, in a city schools division in Laguna, Philippines during 2019 – 2020. Using a descriptive type of research design, the study was conducted among 90 respondents (with 24 males and 66 females) with the use of survey. The instrument was adopted, modified, and validated by pool of experts with reliability analysis carried out and yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.901 which shows the questionnaire reached an excellent reliability. For the statistical tools, the study include frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The study found that the respondents' adaptability was "High" in terms of self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, attitude, and knowledge of competencies. Male respondents appeared to be more adaptable than females. Respondents with age greater than 50 obtained a very high adaptability level compared to the rest of the age groups. Respondents with teaching experience 16 – 20 and greater than 30 years got very high adaptability. In conclusion, the participants were highly adaptable even when they are experiencing the pandemic COVID-19. Thus, it is recommended that teachers should communicate with the persons concerned using any medium and understand their situations, and pursue performing their responsibilities.

Keywords: Adaptability, Public School Teachers, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is known to us as a noble profession. It is a happy thing to become a teacher who molds the learners and helps them achieve their dreams. When learners have reached their life's ambition, the first ones who are joyful are the teachers. However, the novice and even experienced teachers also left this profession. It is evident in the international literature that neophyte teachers and even with years of experience leave the profession for few reasons (Borman & Dowling, 2008; Ingersoll, 2002; Sass et al., 2012; Struyven & Vanthournout, 2014).

What the international teachers experienced might also have been experienced by most of the Filipino teachers. Some teachers left the profession for a job that is different from the field. Based on the researcher's observation, some teachers have applied and worked in industry and production, Business Process Outsourcing, or in the call center, and others. In contrast, others have remained in the profession and become adaptable (Novio, 2019).

We knew that this COVID-19 pandemic brings people so much weariness and anxiety. It makes them shift from a standard way of living into something chaotic, and the situations turn into challenging ones. The usual things a person is doing have shifted. Facing a situation different from the usual one is not that easy. A person needs to be adaptable to survive in his lot.

The Filipino teachers are one of the groups of people affected by the pandemic. In a study by Asio (2021), the author stated that faculty and staff work productively

before the COVID-19 pandemic. They are the front liners in the delivery of the lessons. They are the ones responsible for the success and failure of the learners. Students' both success and failure in the academic performances would somehow depend on the teachers' efforts. Still, they must make efforts for their learners even during pandemic.

The study's result would give some recommendations to the teachers facing varied situations, particularly situations during the COVID-19. Thus, the teachers would learn what to do in performing their responsibilities amidst the pandemic. This aimed to determine the teachers' adaptability in Gulod National High School, Division of Cabuyao, Laguna, in the school year 2020-2021.

Literature Review and Framework

The survival of the fittest theory is also known as adaptation theory. According to King (2018), it is an organism's ability to adapt to changes in the environment and regulate over time. Cherry made the point that adaptation means adjusting to new information and experiences. Additionally, learning is about the environment and adapting to changes in the environment are linked. Behavioral patterns can be adopted in order to accommodate change (Cherry, 2017).

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The research and Career Development Theory were connected. The theory presents a method for both comprehending vocational behavior across the life cycle and for clients to help them attain long-and-a successful careers and work as they age progresses. Its scope involves three vocational orientations: differential, developmental, and dynamic. From an individual differences' perspective, it examines the characteristics of vocational types. The study of developmental psychology looks at human adaptation and tasks at work, occupational changes, and work-related problems. For the purposes of the narrative psychology, it explores how life's thematic details color career goals and why people gravitate toward them in distinct ways. Plans for career development incorporates three basic principles: 1) how the individual cultivates their character as they shape their job; 2) work-based career alignment; 3) functional adaptation (Savickas, 1997).

This study is close to one of the education philosophies, pragmatism. The pragmatic principle goes that only what is experienced or noticed is real. They believe that reality shifts, and that we learn best through integration of our experiences and problems. Formal pragmatism is derived from the Peirce's belief that ideas must lead to action rather than remain only in theory. According to John Dewey, people must adapt to their environment and learn from each other. The approach of schools should stress the themes of social experience every bit as much as on place as time (Cohen, 1999).

These were connected to the present study considering that teachers are facing different work-related changes like making and submitting various reports to the superiors, attending webinars, preparing lessons, presentations, and teaching students from different learning modalities, virtually communicating with the learners, parents, and guardians, and others. Thus, if teachers could not adapt to the activities and rapid changes in the workplace, they tend to quit the profession and seek another job.

Adaptability is a person's skill to change his actions, course, or approach to suit a new situation. People are changing their lifestyles constantly because our world is always changing. When there is a shortage of a commodity in the market, they switch their demand to substitute goods. It is not only about adjusting to a situation or changing something. It covers being able to effect changes during action with smoothness and timeliness, without any significant setbacks. It is necessary to acquire this skill if there are many uncontrollable factors in our environment, such as laws and economic factors (cleverism.com, 2018).

Collie et al. (2018) stated that experiences of change, novelty, and uncertainty are prevalent to all earthlings. These include major events such as moving out of home, beginning school, and beginning a new job. They also include everyday events such as a shift in job role, think of alternative transport when a flat car battery strikes, or have unexpected guests join for dinner. The extent to which we can adjust our thoughts, actions, and emotions to respond successfully to these situations is known as adaptability. It involves adjusting the way we think about the situation to consider different options, undertaking

different actions to better navigate the situation, and minimizing emotions that may be unhelpful or distracting.

Half (n. d.) noted that very few successful people or organizations or organizations got to where they are by only doing the same thing. He added that great leaders seek out change and pursue it feverishly, understanding that to be truly innovative and ahead of trends, one must embrace change. However, being adaptable is not just about embracing change, and being adaptable means being a perpetual optimist and exhibiting extraordinary resilience. Adaptability skills can be possessed both in attitude and action, and one cannot exist without the other.

Boss (2015) stressed that people, teams, and organizations' ability to adapt to changes in their environments, stay relevant, and avoid obsolescence are the defining characteristic between success and failure, growth and stagnation, business, and bankruptcy. To stay relevant as an organization, one needs to think and act adaptively; one needs the right people in the right places, which only comes from how leaders shape their environments.

It appears that adaptable workers are more highly valued than highly skilled workers but may not be as open to change. Solutions must be open to alternatives when the first concept does not work. Other than that, he must be prepared to undertake new activities even if they are outside of his training, flexible enough to find solutions or conceive of ideas, and appreciative of unexpected developments. In addition, he must maintain his composure when things are happening quickly or in a state of stress and demonstrate the competence to perform even while adjusting. Trades, factories, factories, and mining will exist, and technical skills will be required to maintain their employment. Nonetheless, soft skills are becoming increasingly important for workers in all occupations. As two of the most important soft skills will emerge are adaptability and flexibility (Whitehead, 2016). While other studies emphasize on workers', this one's focus is on teachers' adaptability.

Adaptability is vital for teachers. Collie and her colleagues (2018) underlined that just as public life is full of fluctuations, uncertainties, working life is full of new situations for men. The term "just as working life's path is changeable, public service has to them" for instance, in the workplace, teachers come across many learners to whom they must adapt, and respond to changing requirements, as well as unexpected scenarios in the classroom, and colleagues, as well as well as meet, and students, and parents, and all at the same time. These situations call for teachers to be handled in an adaptive manner. Increasing student attention might be done by keeping the lesson on schedule, tolerating failure when a lesson does not go as planned, or adjusting teamwork with new coworkers.

The authors further explained that instructional content must be tailored to students' varying needs, which should be accompanied by changes in learning support as students advance in their understanding of content, and classroom management strategies adjusted as the

students' level of expertise develops. Teachers also need to keep up with changes in the entire school by effectively responding to the demands of their students. Teachers must be able to make changes to their work settings if they are to perform optimally at work (Collie & Martin, 2016).

Jiggs et al. (2014) asked more than 1,100 employers and educators what they thought about the state of employability skills in the UK. The results show that adaptability and communication skills were seen by employers as having grown in importance over the last ten years. More than 60 percent of employers felt adaptability had become more critical over the previous decade. When asked about the importance of skills right now, employers ranked problem-solving as the most important of the seven skills; 19 percent of those surveyed put problem-solving in the first place. Creativity follows (ranked as most important by 17 percent of employers), leadership, and adaptability (both with 16 percent). It suggests that when employers look back over a decade of labor market change or look forward to future changes, communication and adaptability are at the forefront of their minds. In addition, a study showed that teachers have established sleep and religious tasks routines (Asio & Jimenez, 2021).

Researchers stressed that adaptability is something teachers require regularly, and it likely plays a vital role in helping them navigate the demands of their work. Collie and Martin's (2017) prior research found support for this. They found that when teachers are more adaptable, they tend to report better well-being. They also examined whether there were additional connections with students' achievement. Results showed that when teachers were more adaptable and had better well-being, their students had higher achievement (Collie & Martin, 2018). Thus, teachers' adaptability is very significant and much needed in typical situations and pandemic times.

Researchers asked 164 secondary school teachers in Australia to rate their adaptability, their experiences of labor disengagement, and their job commitment. The results showed that teachers tended to report lower work disengagement and, in turn, more outstanding job commitment when they were more adaptable. Adaptable teachers can effectively navigate the constant change, novelty, and uncertainty that occur in teaching. It may aid the teachers avoid the outlooks of helplessness that lead to disengagement. They also asked teachers about the extent to which they felt the principal listens to teachers' perspectives and supports their initiative and innovation. The findings showed that when teachers reported principal support, they tended to be more adaptable (Collie & Martin, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized the descriptive research design through survey questionnaire to gather the profile and the respondents' level of adaptability.

Population and Sampling

The researcher conducted the study at Gulod National High School, City Schools Division of Cabuyao, Laguna. Before the survey's conduct, the researcher sent a permission letter to survey with the Schools Division Superintendent. He also sent a letter to the school head of the responding school and sent the Google Form link to the volunteer-teacher for the survey with an attached consent letter.

Since the researcher distributed the survey through a digital platform, not all target participants have responded with it. Out of 110, there were only 90 or 82% teachers volunteered and answered the survey.

Instrumentation

The researcher used a survey questionnaire that was composed of two parts. The first part was for the respondents' profile. The second part was an adopted questionnaire to measure the respondents' adaptability (Morgan, 2011). The researcher carried out the reliability analysis on an adaptability skills scale comprising 28 items. Cronbach's alpha (0.901) showed the questionnaire reach excellent reliability (Munda & Tamban, 2019). The questionnaire was modified so that it would fit the current situation experienced by the respondents. The research instrument has undergone content validity by asking specialists in the field to judge the appropriateness of the items on the instrument.

Statistical Analysis

The researcher retrieved the responses after one week and generated the spreadsheet from the responses in Google Form. Then, he transferred the data into SPSS version 25 for analysis.

The researcher used the frequency and percentage to determine the profile in terms of sex, age, and teaching years. He used the mean, and standard deviation to describe the respondents' level of adaptability, including the adaptability in terms of sex, age, and years of teaching.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The researcher sought to determine the teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of sex, age, and teaching years in public school. Provided below were the results of the study. The profile of teacher-respondents, according to sex, was presented in Table 1.

Table 1 presents the distribution of teacher-respondents when grouped according to sex. We could observe that female teacher-respondents were greater in quantity than males. From the 90 or 82% respondents out of 110 population of Gulod National High School, City Schools Division of Cabuyao, 24 or 26.7% were males while 66 or 73.3% were females.

Table 2 shows the age distribution of the

Table 1
The Profile of Teacher-respondents according to Sex.

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	26.7
Female	66	73.3
Total	90	100.0

Table 2
The Profile of Teacher-respondents according to Age.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21 – 25	9	10.0
26 – 30	18	20.0
31 – 35	22	24.4
36 – 40	17	18.9
41 – 45	14	15.6
46 – 50	4	4.4
> 50	6	6.7
Total	90	100.0

Table 3
The Profile of Teacher-respondents according to Years of Teaching Experience.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 5	45	50.0
6 – 10	31	34.4
11 – 15	8	8.9
16 – 20	3	3.3
21 – 25	0	0
26 – 30	1	1.1
> 30	2	2.2
Total	90	100.0

Table 4
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents in terms of Self-awareness

Self-awareness	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I can articulate/express my special abilities, talents, and skills.	3.96	0.67	High
2. I know what I have to do to regain my confidence when I temporarily lose it.	4.02	0.67	High
3. I have a strong sense of self-esteem and generally feel good about myself.	4.00	0.64	High
4. I can identify and communicate my weaknesses and the ways that I work with or around them.	3.97	0.53	High
5. I have a vision for my life that gives it meaning and purpose.	4.49	0.55	Very High
6. I know what is important to me and use this knowledge in making decisions.	4.46	0.56	Very High
Overall Self-awareness	4.21	0.48	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Table 5
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents in terms of Personal Management

Personal Management	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I take responsibility for managing my teaching responsibilities.	4.53	0.55	Very High
2. I can see how my job fits into the bigger picture of my life plans.	4.33	0.60	High
3. I have a personal financial plan, which I evaluate regularly based on my current situation.	4.20	0.67	High
4. I have contingency plans, a second option if my first plan does not work out.	4.12	0.71	High
5. I assess my strengths and weaknesses, outline ways to grow, and establish short and long-range goals for my job.	4.20	0.62	High
Overall Personal Management	4.37	0.49	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Table 6
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents in terms of Problem-solving and Decision-making

Problem-Solving and Decision-making	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I have emerged stronger and have learned personal strategies to deal with change because of my life changes.	4.20	0.58	High
2. I can organize my surroundings and prioritize tasks, even in stressful times.	4.11	0.61	High
3. I can find and mobilize necessary resources in a crisis or new situation.	4.06	0.64	High
4. I can usually think of several alternatives to solving a problem.	4.17	0.64	High
5. When experiencing stress in one area of life, I can contain it within that area.	3.86	0.66	High
Overall Problem-solving and Decision-making	4.03	0.54	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

respondents of the study. The table shows 31-35 got most of the respondents' age with 22 or 24.4% teachers while 46 – 50 got the least among the age groups of respondents with 4 or 4.4% teachers.

Table 3 presents the profile of teachers according to years of teaching experience. The teaching experience with the highest frequency was 1 – 5 years with 45 or 50% teachers while 26 – 30 years of teaching experience got the least frequency with 1 or 1.1% respondents with 26 – 30 years. In addition, there were no respondents with teaching experiences from 21 to 25 years.

Table 4 shows the level of adaptability of teacher-respondents in terms of self-awareness. The statement that got the highest level of mean, with very high-level interpretation, was "I have a vision for my life that gives it meaning and purpose" ($X^- = 4.49$), while the one that got the least mean, with high-level descriptive interpretation, was "I can articulate/express my special abilities, talents and skills" ($X^- = 3.96$). The respondents' average mean

level of self-awareness was 4.21.

The fifth table presents the level of adaptability of teacher-respondents in terms of personal management. The statement that got the highest level of mean, with very high-level descriptive interpretation, was "I take responsibility for managing my teaching responsibilities" ($X^- = 4.53$) while "I have contingency plans, a second option if my first plan does not work out" got the lowest mean ($X^- = 4.13$) with an interpretation of high level. The overall mean of the respondents' adaptability in terms of personal management was 4.37.

Table 6 shows the level of adaptability of teacher-respondents in terms of problem-solving and decision-making. All the statements got a high level of descriptive interpretation. The statement that got the highest mean ($X^- = 4.20$) was "I have emerged stronger and have learned personal strategies to deal with change because of the changes in my life," while the one that got the lowest mean ($X^- = 3.86$) was "When experiencing stress in one area of

Table 7
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents in terms of Attitude

Attitude	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I believe that I always have options and choices, even under challenging situations.	4.38	0.59	High
2. I generally approach life as an optimist.	4.30	0.64	High
3. I have a sense of humor. I can find things to laugh about even in dark times.	4.18	0.76	High
4. I understand there is growth in new experiences and enjoy learning from them.	4.48	0.57	High
5. I expect life to have ups and downs and not always go as I would like it to.	4.58	0.58	Very High
6. I do not spend time worrying about things that are out of my control.	3.93	0.79	High
Overall Attitude	4.03	0.54	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Table 8
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents in terms of Knowledge of Competencies

Attitude	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I would describe myself as a continuous learner.	4.62	0.53	Very High
2. I regularly spend time keeping my knowledge and skills in the progress.	4.34	0.58	High
3. I know the skills that will be required in my job in the next several years.	4.28	0.62	High
4. I know what others in our school expect of me.	4.04	0.70	High
5. I know how my superiors and co-teachers view my current skills.	3.99	0.66	High
6. I know which behaviors and attitudes are rewarded in our school.	4.17	0.72	High
Overall Knowledge of Competencies	4.39	0.51	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

life, I can contain it within that area." The average mean on problem-solving and decision-making was 4.03.

The seventh table shows the level of adaptability of teacher-respondents in terms of attitude. "I expect life to have ups and downs and not always go as I would like it to" got the highest mean ($X^- = 4.58$) with very high-level interpretation while "I do not spend time worrying about things that are out of my control" got the lowest mean ($X^- = 3.93$) with an interpretation of high level. The average mean on attitude was 4.03.

The eighth table shows the level of adaptability of teacher-respondents in terms of knowledge of competencies. The statement "I would describe myself as a continuous learner" got the highest mean ($X^- = 4.62$) with a very high-level interpretation, which meant that the respondents view themselves as continuous learners. On the other hand, "I know how my superiors view my current skills and co-teachers" got the lowest mean (3.99) with an interpretation of high level. The average mean on

knowledge of competencies was 4.39.

Table 9 shows that Knowledge of Competencies got the highest mean ($X^- = 4.39$), while Problem-solving and Decision-Making got the lowest mean ($X^- = 4.03$). The average mean was 4.23, which elucidates that the respondents have high adaptability levels.

The researcher sought to explain the teacher-respondents' adaptability level in terms of sex, age, and the number of years of teaching.

The tenth table shows that both males and females had high levels of adaptability. However, based on the results, male respondents ($X^- = 4.28$) appeared to be more adaptable than females ($X^- = 4.21$).

Table 11 shows the level of adaptability of respondents according to age. Respondents with age greater than 50 obtained a very high adaptability level ($X^- = 4.63$) compared to the rest of the age groups. The age group that got the lowest mean ($X^- = 4.09$) was 21 – 25.

Table 9
The Overall Level of Adaptability Skills of Teacher-respondents

Problem-solving and Decision-making	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
Self-awareness	4.21	0.48	High
Personal Management	4.37	0.49	High
Problem-solving and Decision-Making	4.03	0.54	High
Attitude	4.16	0.57	High
Knowledge of Competencies	4.39	0.51	High
Overall Adaptability	4.23	0.42	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Table 10
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents according to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
Male	24	4.21	0.48	High
Female	66	4.37	0.49	High
Total	90	4.03	0.54	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Table 11
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents according to Age

Age	Frequency	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
21 – 25	9	4.09	0.27	High
26 – 30	18	4.19	0.32	High
31 – 35	22	4.26	0.32	High
36 – 40	17	4.19	0.59	High
41 – 45	14	4.18	0.49	High
46 – 50	4	4.27	0.36	High
> 50	6	4.63	0.37	Very High
Total	90	4.23	0.42	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Table 12 shows the level of adaptability of respondents according to teaching experience. Respondents with teaching experience 16 – 20 years and greater than 30 got very high adaptability level ($X^- = 4.73$ and 4.50 respectively). Then, respondents with greater than 30 and 26 – 30 years of experience obtained got a very high level of adaptability with the means 4.50 and 4.60, respectively. Respondents with teaching experience 1 – 5 years got the lowest mean ($X^- = 4.12$).

DISCUSSION

Females were dominant in this study. They belong to 31 – 35 years old and have teaching experience of 1 – 5 years. It was close to the study of Asio (2021), wherein most of his teacher-respondents belong to 21-30 years old, with 1-5 years in service. However, Asio's study was dominated by males and was single.

The teachers in Gulod National High School, City Schools Division of Cabuyao, are highly adaptable even during the pandemic. They have bendable abilities to face the varied situations in the school, including the drastic changes in situations such as changing from physical or face-to-face teaching into blended and modular distance teaching, distribution of modules and week home learning plan, retrieval of students' answer sheets, communicating with students and parents/guardians virtually, attending virtual seminars, and others. As stated by Collie and her colleagues (2018), these situations call for teachers to be handled in an adaptive manner. Additionally, COVID-19 is a new, changing, and uncertain situation for all. It can be said that adaptability is required today more than ever. For teachers, this could, involve adjusting their beliefs and their temperament, for the better or worse, when it comes to how students learn on the internet and helping them find ways, they can use it in teaching (Collie & Martin, 2020).

Table 12
The Level of Adaptability of Teacher-respondents according to Years of Teaching experience

Teaching Experience in Years	Frequency	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1 – 5	45	4.12	0.37	High
6 – 10	31	4.32	0.36	High
11 – 15	8	4.18	0.65	High
16 – 20	3	4.73	0.23	Very High
21 – 25	0	0	0	None
26 – 30	1	4.60	0	Very High
> 30	2	4.50	0.71	Very High
Total	90	4.23	0.42	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Very High Level; 3.50-4.59 = High Level; 2.50-3.49 = Average level; 1.50-2.49 = Fair level; 1.00-1.49 = Poor level

Further, the mean level of adaptability of respondents according to age were not directly proportional to the age groups, but it was safe to surmise that the more mature teachers are, the more adaptable they are with the changing situations. The survey's findings of ARC Centre of Excellence in Population Ageing Research (2019) supported this study. Australian workers aged 65+ were more likely to say that they work because they enjoy it (71%) or it gives them a sense of purpose (71%) compared to their counterparts aged 45 (46%) and younger (47%). 90% of mature employees over the age of 65 say they actively try to develop their capabilities. Managers aged between 45 and 54 report a more remarkable ability to adapt to change than those in any other age group.

Males were more adaptable than the females. The study of Valdivia et al. (2009) contradicted that females ($X^{\bar{}} = 22.82$) were more flexible than males ($X^{\bar{}} = 21.46$). This study also contradicted Anson's (2012) observation that women are more adaptable than men. Anson observed the differences between men and women based on the percentage of decrease in men's work or labor participation from 1954 to 2012. Additionally, this report directly countered the assertion made by the CEO of AT&T, USA, Mr. John Donovan. He stated that he is not a supporter of female advocacy, he is simply making commercial decisions. In these instances, women are more likely to change their behavior than men. Donovan discovered that women have an essential quality that enables them to adjust to a rapid-changing environment (Thomas, 2017).

Although the adaptability means on teaching experience were not directly proportional, respondents with long teaching experience were more adaptable to the changing situations than those novices in teaching. his agrees with Reade (2015), which claims that workers with experience are well equipped to deal with workplace distractions. They do not appear to show any decrease in their productivity or workplace accidents. More experienced workers are more careful. Further, Olsen (2020) mentioned Chapman's statement that senior-level employees have

gone through throughout their career, such as economic crisis, corporate restructure, natural disasters, and disease outbreaks. These practices improved their adaptability because they allow them to pivot and adjust quickly when change occurs.

CONCLUSIONS

Majority of the respondents were females. They belong to 31 – 35 years old and have teaching experience of 1 – 5 years. The results showed that the teacher-respondents' level of adaptability was high-level in terms of self-awareness ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.21$), personal management ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.37$), problem-solving and decision-making ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.03$), attitude ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.16$), and knowledge of competencies ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.39$). Overall, the respondents are highly adaptable even during the pandemic ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.23$).

Further, the researcher concluded that the male teachers ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.28$) were more flexible than the females ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.21$). Teachers with ages greater than fifty had very high adaptability ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.63$). Teachers with experience 16-20 and greater than 26 years were very highly adaptable ($X^{\bar{}} = 4.73$) to the pandemic situation. The participants were highly adaptable even when they are experiencing COVID-19, which has become pandemic.

The researcher limited the study to the adaptability of teachers amidst the pandemic. He surveyed at Gulod National High School, City Schools Division of Cabuyao, Laguna, Philippines in 2020-2021. The participants were limited only to the teachers who would voluntarily answer the survey questionnaire.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following were recommended based on the result and implications of the study:

1. Teachers should communicate with their co-teachers, superiors, students, and parents or guardians using any medium, and understand their situations. They should

- consider the students, for they need understanding and empathy. Teachers should be patient, continuously perform the duties and responsibilities, and find all the ways and means to accomplish the assigned tasks.
2. Superiors should also be considerate of the condition of teachers. When they see teachers tired and stressed, they should give enough time to accomplish the assigned tasks and help the teachers lessen the burden during the pandemic situation.
 3. Students should show respect and cooperation with their teachers, accomplish the activities assigned to them, and ask for guidance from their relatives in performing the tasks. They should ask the teachers when the directions seem vague to them.
 4. Parents should also give their utmost efforts in support for their children by cooperating with the teachers in molding the children to become productive citizens of the community. They should serve as facilitators for their children in answering the activities assigned for without them, children would not have clear directions in performing the learning tasks.
 5. Further research should be made by having the adaptability of teachers correlated with teachers' performance and students' academic performance in certain subjects.

REFERENCES

- Anson, E. (2012). Are women more adaptable than men? <https://bit.ly/3mhz0fe>
- ARC Centre of Excellence in Population Ageing Research. (2019, December). Potential: Findings from the mature workers in organisations survey. Australian research Council. <https://bit.ly/31Q2esd>
- Asio, J. M. R. (2021). Determinants of work productivity among selected tertiary education employees: A pre-COVID-19 pandemic analysis. *International Journal of Didactical Studies*, 2(1), 101455. <https://doi.org/10.3390/IJODS.2021167470>
- Asio, J. M. R., & Jimenez, E. C. (2021). Teachers' sleep, religious tasks, and suicidal thoughts: A preliminary assessment. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(1), 71-79. <https://dx.doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.02.01.02>
- Borman, G. D. & Dowling, N. M. (2008). Teacher attrition and retention: A meta-analytic and narrative review of the research. *Review of Educational Research*, 78(3), 367-409. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654308321455>
- Boss, J. (2015). 14 signs of an adaptable person. <https://bit.ly/3cOchUL>
- Cherry, K. (2017). Adaptation for coping with change. <https://bit.ly/3cMzoPD>
- Cleverism Journal. (n.d). Adaptability skills. <https://bit.ly/3rRuSno>
- Cohen, L. M. (1999). Pragmatism. <https://oregonstate.edu/instruct/ed416/PP2.html>
- Collie, R. J., & Martin, A. J. (2018). Being able to adapt in the classroom improves teachers' well-being. <https://bit.ly/3dz5myb>
- Collie, R. J., & Martin, A. J. (2016). Adaptability: An important capacity for effective teachers. *Educational Practice and Theory*, 38(1), 27-39. <https://doi.org/10.7459/ept/38.1.03>
- Collie, R. J., & Martin, A. J. (2017). Teachers' Sense of adaptability: Examining links with perceived autonomy support, teachers' psychological functioning, and students' numeracy achievement. <https://bit.ly/2R2ERJD>
- Collie, R.J., & Martin, A. J. (2020). Teachers' wellbeing during COVID-19. <https://bit.ly/39KWswf>
- Half, R. (n.d). Adaptability skills. <https://bit.ly/2Q12h1q>
- Ingersoll, R. M. (2002). The teacher shortage: A case of wrong diagnosis and wrong prescription. *NASSP Bulletin*, 86, 16-31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019263650208663103>
- Jiggs, Julia, et. al. (2014). Employer and Educator Perspectives on Employability Skills in the UK. <https://bit.ly/3rO3cQ9>
- King, S. (2018). What is adaptation theory? <https://bit.ly/2Osj7WU>
- Morgan, H. (2011, November 4). Test your adaptability. <https://bit.ly/3umTJB1>
- Munda, N. P., & Tamban, V. E. (2019). Non-cognitive skills and mathematics performance of grade 8 students: An input to student development program. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 6(5), 2137-2148. <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1905U03>
- Novio, E. B. (2019). Teachers now joining diaspora of Filipinos seeking greener pasture. <https://bit.ly/39LDwh4>
- Olsen, S. (2020). Adaptability: Your most essential workplace skill. *Inhersight*. <https://bit.ly/3sVvyJQ>
- Reade, N. (2015). The surprising truth about older workers. *AARP The Magazine*. <https://bit.ly/3fMFlxV>
- Sass, D. A., Flores, B. B., Claeys, L. & Perez, B. (2012). Identifying personal and contextual factors that contribute to attrition rates for Texas public school teachers. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 20(15), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v20n15.2012>
- Savickas, M. L. (1997). Career adaptability: An integrative construct for life-span, life-space theory. *Career Development*, 45, 247-259. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-0045.1997.tb00469.x>
- Struyven, K. & Vanthournout, G. (2014). Teachers' exit decisions: An investigation into the reasons why newly qualified teachers fail to enter the teaching profession or why those who do enter do not continue teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 43, 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2014.05.005>

org/10.1016/j.tate.2014.06.002

Whitehead, J. (2016). How flexible are you? The Soft Skill of Adaptability. <https://bit.ly/3cOL58s>

Thomas, S. (2017). AT&T's Donovan: Women adapt faster than men. <https://bit.ly/3mi8kuS>

Valdivia, O. D., & Cañada, M. A. (2009). Changes in flexibility according to gender and educational stage. <https://bit.ly/39IuvVL>